

Blood products are used to treat a multitude of diseases, so the blood transfusion system needs to be enhanced. CRISPR/Cas9 has made it viable to make HLA class I-deleted blood products to avoid rejection

Moataz Dowaidar^{1,2}

¹Department of Bioengineering, King Fahd University of Petroleum and Minerals (KFUPM), Dhahran 31261, Saudi Arabia.

²Interdisciplinary Research Center for Hydrogen and Energy Storage (IRC-HES), King Fahd University of Petroleum and Minerals (KFUPM), Dhahran, 31261, Saudi Arabia

Abstract:

In adults, normal hematopoiesis occurs in the bone marrow, producing leukocytes, red blood cells, and platelets. Recently, megakaryocytes have been found in mouse lungs and spleen, where they release platelets by blood flow force. Blood products are used to treat a multitude of diseases and conditions that generate cytopenia. The blood transfusion system must be enhanced due to a drop in blood donors due to low birth rate and changing attitudes among young people, pathogen contamination, and rising demand due to chronic blood diseases that are prevalent among the elderly. Pluripotent stem cells, such as embryonic stem (ES) cells, may proliferate in vitro indefinitely and are a prospective source for blood transfusions to replace blood donations.

Platelet preparations can be maintained at room temperature to sustain platelet function, but only have a statutory expiry date of five days. Platelets are anucleate cells, thus irradiation before blood donation can lessen the risk of iPS cell infection. Effective treatment requires HLA-compatible platelet transfusions, although supply limits often leave patients underserved. CRISPR/Cas9 has made it viable to make HLA class I-deleted blood products to avoid rejection and lower the odds of platelet-expressed human leukocyte antigen Class I cancer-causing iPS cells (HLA-I). This article discusses the production of megakaryocyte cell lines, bioreactors, and scale-up cultures, as well as identifying viable drugs in manufacturing. HLA-null, iPSC-derived platelet products' universal potential will also be explored.

Introduction

In adults, normal hematopoiesis takes place in the bone marrow, where leukocytes, red blood cells, and platelets are produced. Fetal hematopoiesis, on the other hand, occurs in distinct locations and at different stages of development. There are two stages of fetal hematopoiesis development: primitive hematopoiesis, which occurs transiently in the yolk sac during the early stages of the embryo, and definitive hematopoiesis, which begins after primary hematopoiesis and moves from the aorta-gonad-mesonephros (AGM) to the liver, then to the bone marrow. By fulfilling three key functions: oxygen supply, coagulation, and immunity, the blood system keeps and protects our bodies. Megakaryocytes in the bone marrow release platelets, which have a clotting role and circulate as anucleate blood cells. Mature megakaryocytes elongate a cytoplasmic structure termed the proplatelet in normal thrombocytosis. The proplatelet's tip extends into the bone marrow sinus, where it gets sheared and transformed into a platelet by the circulation (Junt et al., 2007; Kosaki, 2008; Machlus & Italiano, 2013; Thon et al., 2010). Megakaryocytes have recently been discovered in the mouse lung and spleen, where they release platelets by the force of blood flow (Lefrançois et al., 2017).

Blood products obtained from blood donors are used to treat a number of illnesses and disorders that induce cytopenia (Estcourt et al., 2017). However, the blood transfusion system has to be strengthened owing to a

decrease in blood donors due to low birthrates and changing attitudes among the young population, pathogen contamination, and increased demand owing to chronic blood illnesses, which are widespread among the elderly. Platelet preparations can be stored at room temperature to retain platelet function, but they only have a five-day statutory expiration date. As a result, platelet preparations are difficult to have on hand. Furthermore, some patients have alloantibodies against platelet-expressed human leukocyte antigen class I (HLA-I), resulting in alloimmune platelet transfusion refractoriness (allo-PTR; Stanworth et al., 2015). HLA-compatible platelet transfusions are required for effective therapy, yet supply limitations frequently leave patients underserved. Pluripotent stem cells, such as embryonic stem (ES) cells (Thomson, 1998) and induced pluripotent stem (iPS) cells (Takahashi et al., 2007), may grow forever in vitro and are a promising source for developing blood transfusion products as a replacement for blood donations. Platelets are anucleate cells, hence irradiation prior to blood donation can reduce the danger of cancer from iPS cell contamination. Furthermore, there is potential to supplement the present donor-dependent blood transfusion system by providing a steady supply of HLA-compatible platelets by using stored iPS cells with homozygous HLA. More recently, genetic editing techniques like the CRISPR/Cas9 approach have made it feasible to manufacture HLA class I-deleted blood products to avoid rejection (Cong et al., 2013; Mali et al., 2013). The creation of megakaryocyte cell lines, bioreactors, and scale-up cultures, as well as the identification of viable pharmaceuticals in manufacturing, are all discussed in this article. The universal potential of HLA-null, iPSC-derived platelet products will also be discussed.

Megakaryocyte Hematopoiesis Development

Hematopoiesis begins during ontogeny with a process known as primitive hematopoiesis. For many years, researchers have studied hematopoietic development, mostly in mice. The creation of structures termed blood islands in the yolk sac, an extrafetal membrane tissue that surrounds the embryo from around day 7 of the fetal phase, is the earliest recorded event of hematopoiesis in mice (Moore & Metcalf, 1970). The majority of fetal red blood cells containing fetal hemoglobin are formed in blood islands (Silver & Palis, 1997), but macrophages (Palis et al., 1999) and megakaryocytes (Tober et al., 2007) are also formed. Around day 10 of the fetal phase, definitive hematopoiesis begins with the generation of hematopoietic stem cells (HSCs) from the AGM area in the fetus, with the produced HSCs moving to the liver (Medvinsky & Dzierzak, 1996). The HSCs then repeatedly self-renew and differentiate on day 16 of the fetal period (Ema & Nakauchi, 2000), growing themselves and a range of adult blood cells at the same time. The fetal liver is the primary site of hematopoiesis immediately after birth, but HSCs migrate to the bone marrow shortly before birth, where hematopoiesis also occurs, and in adults is the site of hematopoiesis throughout life. Long-term (LT) HSCs may be transplanted into mice with diminished hematopoietic capability (Osawa et al., 1996), whereas short-term (ST) HSCs have pluripotency but only transitory self-renewal ability (Osawa et al., 1996). (Christensen & Weissman, 2001). As the cells develop from ST-HSCs, they become multipotent progenitors (MPPs), which lack the potential to self-renew. MPPs will be the progenitors of all blood cells in the future. Following that, progenitors in the lymphoid system, such as common myeloid progenitors (CMP), granulocyte/monocyte progenitors (GMP), megakaryocyte/erythroblast progenitors (MEP), and common lymphoid progenitors (CLP), were purified and identified, and the pathways of their hematopoietic differentiation system were clarified (Akashi et al., 2000; Kondo et al., 1997). HSCs are differentiated into MPPs, CMPs, and MEPs, which are megakaryocyte progenitors, according to the traditional concept of megakaryopoiesis. Thrombopoietin (TPO), which is mostly generated by the liver, is an essential cytokine for megakaryocyte development (Bartley et al., 1994; Kaushansky et al., 1994). In addition, cytokines such as interleukin (IL)-3 (Teramura et al., 1988), IL-6 (Navarro et al., 1991), IL-11 (Broudy et al., 1995), GM-CSF (Briddell et al., 1991), SCF (Briddell et al., 1991), and LIF (Metcalf et al., 1991) have been found to promote TPO interacts to a single transmembrane receptor called c-MPL, which dimerizes when TPO attaches. Following that, phosphorylation of tyrosine residues on the c-MPL receptor activates the JAK2/STATs pathway, as well as MAPKs and PI3K/Akt via RAS, leading to the production of a collection of megakaryocyte differentiation genes (Beer et al., 2008; Drachman et al., 1995; Grozovsky et al., 2015). GATA-1 and FLI-1, which are also involved in the control of *mpl* gene expression and differentiation into erythrocytes and megakaryocytes in MEP fractions, are transcription factors involved in megakaryocyte differentiation (Deveaux et al., 1996; Frontelo et al., 2007; Stachura et al., 2006). The transcriptional control of megakaryocyte differentiation has been linked to the FOG1/GATA1 complex, RUNX1, and FLI-1 during megakaryocyte maturation (Lordier et al., 2012; Shimizu et al., 2004, 2009; Wang et al., 2002). NF-E2 increases the formation of proplatelets in mature megakaryocytes, hence contributing to platelet production, and also modulates platelet activity (Levin et al., 1999; Shivdasani et al., 1995). Although the above outlines the traditional paradigm for megakaryocyte and platelet development, HSCs have recently been shown to include megakaryocyte repopulating progenitors (MKrPs) (Yamamoto et al., 2013). MKrPs are destined to develop into megakaryocytes straight from HSCs. Furthermore, certain HSCs that express von Willebrand factor (vWF), a protein found on megakaryocytes, have been shown to develop directly into megakaryocytes (Sanjuan-Pla et al., 2013). MPPs were also separated into four groups (MPP1-4), each with a distinctive skewed differentiation

lineage. MPP2 is particularly prone to megakaryocyte and erythrocyte differentiation (Pietras et al., 2015). MPP2 has also been observed to develop into megakaryocytes directly (Rodríguez-Fraticelli et al., 2018).

Benefits Of Blood Products Made From Ips Cells

In vitro, pluripotent stem cells (iPS cells) have the ability to self-renew and can grow forever. Understanding the developmental mechanism might be aided by reconstructing the hematopoietic system using iPS cells. Furthermore, iPS cells derived from individual individuals can be utilized for disease modeling, assisting in pathology research and medication testing. Because iPS cells can readily be genetically modified using CRISPR/Cas9 and other technologies, the role of individual genes in development and disease may be investigated. Patients' own cells and highly immunocompatible iPS cells might be used as source cells in regenerative medicine. Based on previous studies using ES cells, iPS cells have been successfully differentiated into various types of blood cells, including lymphocytes (Nishimura et al., 2013; Themeli et al., 2013; Vizcardo et al., 2013), myeloid cells (Haruta et al., 2013), erythrocytes (Hirose et al., 2013; Kurita et al., 2013), erythr The nonpathogenicity of iPS cell-derived blood products is ensured through sterile manufacture from source cells without the risk of infection, and the supply is not dependent on blood donors. The creation of diverse blood cell lines that can self-replicate and be cryopreserved from iPS cells would result in a huge number of safe and functioning blood cell lines that could be kept in a master cell bank. It would be able to generate blood products of assured clinical grade quality by following good manufacturing practice or good gene, cellular, and tissue-based products manufacturing practice (GCTP) standards for the manufacturing process after freezing.

Platelet Differentiation With Es And Ips Cells

In Japan, a single platelet transfusion contains 10 units (about 200 billion platelets). We and other organizations have developed a way to increase the enormous numbers of iPS cells from which we manufacture megakaryocytes and platelets by utilizing the indefinite self-renewal capability of iPS cells. ES/iPS cell-derived sac-like structures (ES/iPS-sac) are produced in our differentiation approach by co-culturing mouse fetal 10T1/2 cells with ES/iPS cells in the presence of vascular endothelial growth factor (VEGF) (VEGF). The sac is filled with blood progenitor cells. By growing these progenitor cells in the presence of soluble factors like SCF and TPO, they may be directly differentiated into megakaryocytes and platelets (Takayama et al., 2008, 2010).

In vivo, the obtained platelets produce thrombi. Using the EB technique, Feng et al. were able to differentiate iPS cells directly into megakaryocytes and platelets in a feeder-free, serum-free medium with no animal components (Feng et al., 2014). They also used the TALEN approach to develop genetically altered HLA-null iPS cells into megakaryocytes and platelets, demonstrating that the platelets have functional ability. Hansen et al. used a monolayer differentiation system to differentiate single iPS cells into blood progenitor cells in a feeder-free, serum-free environment, and then differentiated the progenitor cells into megakaryocyte, erythroid, and myeloid cells (Hansen et al., 2018). Due to the intricacy of the procedures and the lengthy incubation periods necessary, none of these approaches have been established for practical application. We developed a novel technique to immortalize megakaryocytes as a remedy to the challenges mentioned above.

Creation Of Immortalized Megakaryocyte Cell Lines From Ips Cells

We discovered that the expression of c-MYC is elevated during the proliferation phase of megakaryocyte progenitor cells but inhibited during the maturation phase of megakaryocytes using our prior ES/iPS cells differentiation method (Takayama et al., 2010). As a result, c-MYC transgenic mice had a higher megakaryocyte population than wild type mice, but no significant difference in platelet numbers (WT; Thompson et al., 1996). c-MYC knockout animals, on the other hand, have low-ploidy (8N) megakaryocytes and high MPV platelets. Furthermore, c-MYC knockout animals had higher megakaryocyte and platelet numbers than WT mice (Guo et al., 2009). Controlled c-MYC expression may be critical for megakaryocyte proliferation and maturation, according to these findings. Overexpression of c-MYC in blood progenitors produced from ES cells boosted megakaryocyte proliferation for a short time before inducing cellular senescence and death. Because the polycomb complex component BMI1 and the BCL2 family member BCL-XL repress the cellular senescence-inducing INK4A/ARF gene locus and apoptosis, we were able to create immortalized megakaryocyte cell lines (imMKCLs) by transferring the c-MYC and BMI1 genes, followed by the BCL-XL gene, into human iPS/ES-derived hematopoietic cells (Nakamura et al., 2014). Because these three genes are controlled by the Tet-On system in our system, adding doxycycline causes imMKCLs to proliferate with the expression of the three genes switched on (DOX ON), but removing doxycycline causes imMKCLs to mature and release platelets (DOX OFF). We proposed a system to produce a large number of clinically applicable platelets from these imMKCL master cells by liquid culture in

accordance with good manufacturing practice or GCTP clinical grade standards by stocking large quantities of imMKCL strains as a master cell bank and confirming their safety and high productivity.

The high expense, however, necessitates optimizing the cultural media conditions. In the initial imMKCL medium, expensive recombinant proteins such as stem cell factor (SCF) and thrombopoietin (TPO) were required, but we have recently created a TPO-like agonist, small molecule TA-316 (Aihara et al., 2017). Under 37°C culture conditions, we discovered KP-457, which inhibits a disintegrin and metalloprotease 17 (ADAM17) activity that cleaves the extracellular surface of the vWF receptor GPIb (CD42b) (Hirata et al., 2017).

Meanwhile, Moreau et al. created forward programmed megakaryocytes (fopMKs), a cryopreservable and expandable megakaryocyte cell line, by forcing the expression of GATA1, FLI1, and TAL1 during iPS cell differentiation into megakaryocytes (Moreau et al., 2016). Ono et al. used a non-iPS cell strategy to generate human and mouse fibroblasts to become megakaryocytic cells by overexpressing NF-E2, Maf-G, and Maf-K. (Ono et al., 2012). They also created megakaryocytes from a human adipose-derived mesenchymal stem cell line that proliferated for over two months (Tozawa et al., 2019). If ideal large-scale growing conditions are obtained, these cell lines might likewise be a useful source.

Novel Physical Factors In In Vivo Platelet Production Discovered

Feeder cells are required for imMKCL culture throughout the proliferation and maturation stages (adhesion dependent), but a feeder cell-independent culture is required for therapeutic use. We effectively developed imMKCLs in a 100-ml flask and a 1–20-L WAVE bag system with modest rocking motion without feeder cells throughout the development phase. The combination of Rho-associated protein kinase (ROCK) inhibitors (Gobbi et al., 2013) and aryl hydrocarbon receptor (AhR) antagonists (Strassel et al., 2016) was discovered to permit platelet synthesis under feeder-free settings throughout the maturation phase (Ito et al., 2018).

The cytoplasm spreads from megakaryocytes in the bone marrow to the lumen of blood vessels, where the tips of the protrusions are cleaved by blood flow stimulation, according to two-photon microscopy (Junt et al., 2007). Shear stress is thought to be the primary cause of cytoplasmic cleavage. Various organizations, including ours, have built bioreactors based on the principle of shear stress (Avanzi et al., 2016; Di Buduo et al., 2015; Nakagawa et al., 2013). By loading human umbilical vein endothelial cells (HUVECs) and extracellular matrix components onto a chip, Thon et al. created a microfluidic platelet bioreactor that mimicked the bone marrow environment (Thon et al., 2014). Blin et al. created a bioreactor with numerous vWF-coated micropillars that function as megakaryocyte anchors to efficiently enable shear stress on megakaryocytes (Blin et al., 2016). We assumed that shear stress alone does not fully depict the bone marrow environment since platelet formation efficiency was poor in all reactors. As a result, we used two-photon microscopy and particle image velocimetry (PIV) to further investigate platelet manufacturing locations in the bone marrow. We discovered that platelets were sheared and liberated from proplatelets at a bloodstream site exposed to turbulence, indicating that turbulence plays a physical role in platelet creation as well (Ito et al., 2018).

Production Of Platelet Preparations From Ips Cells

We cultivated imMKCLs in a 2.4-L vertical reciprocal motion liquid culture bioreactor (VerMES) with adjustable turbulent physical conditions, based on the findings that turbulence contributes to platelet formation in vivo. We were able to produce iPS cell-derived platelets that operate similarly to platelets in vivo in a very efficient manner using this method (about 80 platelets per megakaryocytes).

Using 0.3-L and 2.4-L VerMES, a simulated study of physical characteristics and platelet generation in culture vessels under various turbulence conditions was explored. The ideal levels of shear stress and turbulent energy were discovered to be independent of the VerMES culture vessel's volume. As a result, in an 8-L VerMES, we tuned shear stress and turbulent energy to create 100 billion functioning platelets. The ultrastructures of iPS cell-derived platelets and platelets in vivo were shown to be identical using electron microscopy. Watanabe et al. (2017) used thrombocytopenic mouse and rabbit models to establish that the iPS cell-derived platelets exhibited a hemostatic capability similar to donor platelets (Ito et al., 2018).

We hypothesized that essential components that promote platelet production may be liberated from imMKCLs in VerMES cultures since a microarray examination of imMKCLs cultivated in VerMES and static cultures revealed nearly no change in gene expression patterns (Ito et al., 2018). When comparing the VerMES culture to the culture under static circumstances, proteomic analysis of the culture supernatant indicated an increase in the secretion of six proteins in the VerMES culture. Surprisingly, adding VerMES culture supernatant to the static culture had little

influence on platelet formation, suggesting that soluble factors and physical stimuli, namely shear stress, collaborate to promote platelet development. Sardilysin (NRDC; Nishi, 2013), macrophage migration inhibitory factor (MIF; Strüßmann et al., 2013), and insulin-like growth factor binding protein 2 (IGFBP2; Coppé et al., 2008) have all been demonstrated to increase platelet production. Proplatelet production was dramatically decreased in cultures lacking MIF or IGFBP2, according to observations made in a microfluidic chip setting. Further research revealed that proplatelet production was hampered in the absence of MIF and IGFBP2 due to decreased extracellular matrix secretion. NRDC was found in a turbulent milieu surrounding proplatelets and is thought to be involved in endopeptidase-mediated fragmentation of the proplatelets (Nishi, 2013). In conclusion, turbulent flow stimulation is thought to stimulate the development of proplatelets via an autocrine process that eventually cleaves the cell membrane utilizing shear stress to produce platelets.

Differences In Megakaryocyte Maturation And Platelet Production Between In Vitro And In Vivo

Adult megakaryocytes in the bone marrow mature into giant polyploid cells with chromosome numbers ranging from 16N to 124N, migrate into the vascular niche, come into contact with collagen type IV in the vein's basement membrane, and form proplatelet protrusions to release platelets into the bloodstream (Semeniak et al., 2016). Megakaryocytes produced from iPS cells, on the other hand, are mostly weakly polyploid cells, ranging from 2N to 32N. (Takayama et al., 2010). Similarly, megakaryocytes generated in vitro from CD34+ cells from the peripheral blood range from 2N to 32N. (Liu et al., 2011). In vitro, proplatelet production begins as protrusions at various sites along the cell membrane, which elongate and release platelets.

A single MK in the bone marrow is expected to generate 800–2,000 platelets, whereas imMKCLs produce just 60–80 platelets per cell. Furthermore, iPS-derived platelets can be as big as 2–10 μ m in size, compared to 2–4 μ m in vivo. After injection in mice, the big iPS-derived platelets were observed to be fractured by blood flow (Ito et al., 2018). It is currently considered that the involvement of the vascular niche and bone marrow environment has not been adequately adapted to culture conditions in vitro due to poor polyploid and platelet generation in vitro compared to in vivo.

Hla Compatibility With Ips Cell-Derived Platelets

Sensitization and antibody generation against non-self HLA-I can occur as a result of pregnancy or frequent platelet transfusion. As a result, 5–15 percent of patients undergoing platelet transfusions have allo-PTR, a rejection of transfused platelets due to incompatibility with primarily HLA-I. HLA-matched platelets are required for these individuals, which may not be accessible in rare cases or in emergencies (Stanworth et al., 2015). Allo-PTR can be dealt with in a number of ways by iPS cell-derived platelets. To begin, autologous platelets can be created by generating iPS cells from the patient (<https://jrct.niph.go.jp/en-latest-detail/jRCTa050190117>). This product is totally compatible with nature, including HLA and human platelet antigen (HPA), an alloantigen on platelets that can produce allo-PTR and post-transfusion purpura, in which platelet counts drop even more after the transfusion (Semple et al., 2011; Stanworth et al., 2015). However, generating autologous platelets for each individual is expensive and time-consuming.

Alternatively, our institute and others have been stocking homozygous HLA haplotypes in iPS cells (Turner et al., 2013; Umekage et al., 2019). These cells are extremely compatible. According to estimates, the ten most common lines of iPSCs with homozygous HLA might cover around half of the Japanese population. Finally, HLA-I negated iPS cell-derived platelets have been generated thanks to the capacity of gene editing iPS cells (Feng et al., 2014; Gras et al., 2013; Suzuki et al., 2020) These cells can be used as a universal product without the need for a library of HLA haplotypes. Furthermore, they can be used as a substrate for further modified products, perhaps leading to innovative platelet therapeutics.

Conclusion

Thirteen years have elapsed since the development of human iPS cells was announced in 2007. Platelets produced from iPS cells have been generated in sufficient quantities for therapeutic transfusions. As a result, in 2019 (<https://jrct.niph.go.jp/en-latest-detail/jRCTa050190117>), a first-in-human clinical study using autologous iPSC-derived platelets in patients with allo-PTR was launched. One of the current challenges is lowering manufacturing costs. In this context, additional maturation of imMKCLs is required by developing a culture system that replicates the in vivo environment. Further advancements will reach industrialized levels in the future, allowing for the development of new medical systems that will enable safe and ready transfusion systems in any situation.

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